

BRANDING OF TOURISM DESTINATION IN PROMOTION OF TOURISM SERVICES

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***Abstract.** The promotion of tourism services is currently experiencing the highest degree of evolution due to the widespread use in this process of digital technologies and classical methods of promoting services in the field of tourism. Despite this, modern tourism services need new approaches to promotion both on the national and foreign markets in the face of growing competition. The development of tourist destinations is impossible without the active promotion of their tourist product. The relevance of branding tourist destinations is also due to the negative consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic, in the context of which there have been significant changes in the tourism industry. Under these conditions, the creation of a sustainable brand of a tourist destination will minimize future and existing risks caused by internal and external environmental factors. An analysis of the modern experience of branding world tourist destinations shows with all confidence that this is an effective tool that can be multilaterally developed through the use of various applied tools. Among the most promising are the creation of a recognizable logo, slogan, the formation of the image and image of the destination, and many others. The main marketing task in this case is to create an integrated approach to branding a tourist destination that combines the entire range of effective promotion tools, as well as taking into account the system of relationships between them. Creating a brand is an important stage in the development of a marketing strategy for the development of a tourist destination.*

***Keywords:** branding, promotion, tourist destination, tourist services.*

The tourism industry is rightfully considered as a rather specific area of the economy. This is confirmed by the fact that not only tourism organizations, firms directly related to tourism as a sector, but also representatives of the hotel, restaurant transport, entertainment and other sectors are involved in shaping the tourism product. That is why a complex tourist image of the destination, including the following components is formed in the consumer's mind: tourist "magnets", attractions; infrastructure facilities; accessibility in its different sense (transport, visa, etc.); event activities (concerts, exhibitions, etc.); additional services (security, medical care, telecommunications, banks, etc.).

The presented complexity proves that destinations need branding in order to stand out among competitors in the tourism market. The image formed through branding is not created only once. The image of tourist destination that is fixed in the minds of potential clients needs permanent changes and flexible unique project approach in order to create an attractive selling proposition. In this regard, tourism destination branding is an opportunity for constant development with regular amendments and improvement of the offer to potential tourists in accordance with the current requirements of the tourist market. Thus, the image and brand of a destination are related concepts that determine the directions of marketing policy of cities, countries, regions and other destinations. It is extremely important to carry out brand-building at the destination level, which will increase the level of promotion of a tourist destination, both at the national and international levels.

When branding a tourist destination the main objectives are to design, consolidate, spread and develop a positive image of the destination by ensuring its attractiveness for tourists. The objectives of tourist destination branding are very diverse, because they depend on the approach that is used to promote the tourist destination. This can include a set of activities, a critical strategy and individual projects. On the basis of the most suitable approach for promotion the decision to develop specific actions is made. Then the effectiveness of each action is evaluated separately and a conclusion on further ways of improvement is formulated.

When branding a territory it is important to understand the close relationship between the positive image of individual regions, the nearest districts, which have a general impact on the

image of the territory considered for world-wide branding. Therefore, often branded territories make up a kind of bright mosaic of a number of promotion tools that complement one another and form a unique image of the entire state, country, region. Based on this conclusion, it is clear that in order to strengthen and enhance the tourist image of the whole state, it is necessary to work competently with individual tourist destinations, representing this country.

The destination in the tourism sector is a crucial and very important element of the overall structure of tourism. Thus, it can be defined as a kind of nucleus with a set of conditions, a quality service culture and a unique range of services to satisfy and provide for all the necessary tourist needs. Destination in tourism includes a set of significant and substantial elements necessary to attract tourists. The area or region of a tourist destination represents a momentous element in the tourism field, as the touristic destinations themselves as well as their image attracts tourists, creates motivation for a visit, thereby enlivening the whole structure of tourism.

In order to change the status of an ordinary territory to an attractive tourist destination, the following conditions must be met:

- the creation and improvement of places that meet the conditions of comfortable living;
- the provision of high quality services, catering, entertainment facilities;
- highly developed comfortable transport that meets all modern requirements;
- unique attractions that create interest among tourists (it is necessary to create an individual feature of a destination to attract flows of tourists);
- the informativity, availability of communication systems as an effective tool to inform the tourist market, as well as to generate interest in the destination.

However, these activities alone are not enough for tourists to fully realize the attractiveness of a destination, it is necessary to create a sustainable brand of the destination and its promotion.

The problem of many global tourist destinations, as the analysis shows, is the acute need for rebranding, many destinations do not receive proper promotion, despite the existing potential. Many destinations have an image that is far from ideal; it is not clear, undefined, and even to some extent often negative. It is logical that these problems hinder the tourist development of the territory, because it is difficult to find investors for the full development of the destination, to attract tourists, to develop the infrastructure of the destination. Therefore, the creation and development of a territorial brand is a complex process, which requires the elaboration of strategic plans for a long period and confidence in consumer loyalty over the long run. In order to better understand and apply the practices and the successful experience of a territory branding, it is necessary to study the views of different authors on this issue.

The value orientations, as well as the interests of the states in any spheres can be very different, and in this case, if we do not study the public sentiment of another state, the news will not be heard or, even worse, it is possible to lose the trust of the audience [6, p. 149]. It follows that territory branding is a purposeful formation of the image of a country, region or city in the eyes of the local and world community. The purpose of territory branding is to ensure long-term beneficial market positioning, brand presence in the media, brand awareness, and to attract investment to the territory [6, p. 150]. In other words, destination branding is the process of creating a certain image of the territory, the result of which is a long-term effect that influences the formation of loyalty and commitment of a particular tourist area or location among tourists.

Among other authors dealing with these issues, the representatives of the Stockholm School of Economics should be mentioned. According to their ideas, the branding of a territory allows to sell real goods "at a higher price" through an advertising campaign aimed at demonstrating the advantages of the territory to entrepreneurs. In terms of marketing, it is possible to consider inhabitants, tourists, investors as customers, and countries, regions, cities as goods [3, p. 250]. Modern foreign researchers form the latest direction of territorial brand management, in which territory branding is an accurate process of determining the resources of places from the perspective of their predominantly valuable assets [2, p. 56]. These definitions emphasize that territories can themselves act as peculiar goods to which marketing tools can be applied. The territory's brand is the region's brand, which is the main factor in the formation of resources.

The well-being of a tourism destination brand has a direct impact on ensuring a sustainable and favorable image of the destination, mobilizing external investment, increasing economic and entrepreneurial potential, increasing cooperation and integration links and communicating regional achievements and initiatives.

The well-known theoretical experience of various authors, continues to contribute to the improvement of the marketing approach on mastering territorial branding. For example, territorial branding can be the main instrument of territorial marketing regulation, focused on the promotion of communication capital of a destination as a component of institutional capital, the existence of which allows the subjects of territorial marketing to comply with the savings on transaction costs in cooperation [4, p. 77]. It is also proposed to consider territorial branding as a process of brand formation and management, which includes brand promotion and development in its own composition. Among the fundamental objectives of territorial branding it is necessary to outline the following:

- maintaining its own position in the domestic market, including brand promotion in the foreign market;
- increasing the area's resources;
- conveying to people the good qualities of the area, based on individuality;
- carrying out activities aimed at the development of the region.

In a real sense, brand functions are seen as a reflection of the exceptional aspects of a destination, including the historical background of the territory, its indigenous structure, political, economic, social and technological aspects, and as organizing the overall image of a tourist destination, prestigious and obvious to the target clientele [5, p. 28]. It is difficult to imagine destination brand without its traditional attributes. A sustainable destination brand should include a set of components, such as name, logo, slogan, mission, unique selling proposition of the destination. The brand of a tourist destination is seen as the image of the destination, fixed in the consciousness and perception of the consumer. Its concept demonstrates the creative ideas, which are built on the symbolization of the basic values and resources of the territory, embodied in graphic, animation, numerical, semantic and sound expressions. The formation of the territory's brand is based on the marketing approach and its characteristic tools: to comprehend the place of a tourist destination at the world level in its entirety, to discover the main motivations and to identify the preferences of potential consumers. The position in the world tourism market is identified by the reputation of the territory, which is associated with its geographical location, as well as external factors [1, p. 215]. Motivation and preferences of potential consumers depend not only on the attractiveness of the destination, but also on the degree of travel security, so in addition to tourism resources, it needs to be stable and reliable in all aspects of the country.

The work on destination branding to promote tourism services begins with the formation of an appropriate mission for the country or region in which the destination is located. Then individual destinations that can attract the attention of tourists are identified. Specific destinations are selected for their target audience, in other words, as many potential consumers as possible. Then the principles of functioning, management and development of the country or region where the destination is located are formed:

- An impeccable reputation is the sum of beliefs or opinions about a destination; it must be built, protected, maintained and changed, if necessary, over time.;
- Continuous maintenance of an identity that should be based on authenticity, the unique advantages of the destination, permanence and a strong identity.;
- The application of an intangible experience – the perception consists mainly of intangible experience, although tangible experience also matters, and it is subjective in the consumers' consciousness.

These principles will be used by the creators of the future destination brand in the process of assigning an image for the brand, which visitors and tourists will have to remember.

The factors forming the look and image of a tourist destination are the following: natural, landscape and climatic conditions; geographical location; ecology; availability of recreational

areas; types of tourism and their diversity (each separate territory can attract its type or variety of services); means of comfortable accommodation; opportunities for cultural and leisure activities (various entertainment events, animation); fashion trends of the tourist market; territorial mythologem (legends, development history), the uniqueness of the tourist offer and others. In this regard, the authors identified three main groups of requirements for the territory brand:

A. General or formal:

- the brand name should be short and clear;
- the brand name must be unique;
- the brand name must be emotionally expressive and evocative;
- the printed brand should be easy to pronounce and read.

B. Substantive:

- the main idea of positioning;
- the main difference from competitor destinations;
- unique trade offer of the destination;
- brand value for the visitors of the destination;
- information about the high level of service within the destination;
- the lifestyle and standard of living of the consumers and local residents of the destination;
- price segment.

C. Legal:

- When developing the brand, it is necessary to take into account the existing consumer perceptions of the country's global specialization in tourism, its established image and the peculiarities of the national character.

Thus, the creation of tourist destination brand can become a stage or direction of destination marketing strategy. This statement is justified by the fact that individual tools of promotion, branding do not perform their tasks as fully as when they interact in the framework of an integrated approach to the branding of a tourist destination.

A territory's brand can be considered successful if a positive image is formed, which evokes clear associations. For example, Paris - the city of love, Dubai - the center of luxury, the city that grew up in the middle of the desert, the United States - the country of freedom, where dreams easily come true.

Conclusions

The theory of territory branding is constantly developing. In recent years the number of scientific studies devoted to this topic has increased. Every year the interest in branding increases, because the competition between destinations is becoming more and more active. They compete in attracting talent and investment, developing tourism, hosting sports and cultural events, and other areas in which they plan to develop and renew themselves. According to the authors, an interdisciplinary approach to tourist destination branding will begin to prevail in the future. It will reflect the need for a variety of theoretical justifications and the need to capture the fullness and multidimensionality of this type of branding.

When branding tourist destinations it is necessary to develop projects aimed at promoting the tourist product. The project concept should be very unique, effective and independent of traditional approaches. At the same time, it should combine the capabilities of business and society in order to distinguish it from other major projects in the market that can compete in the field of tourism.

Therefore, the role of tourist destination branding in the promotion of tourism services is undeniable. However, it requires timely and regular adjustments and specially designed program of change and formation of a new updated attractive image. Such measures will lead to an increase in the share of the tourist market and thereby will give the opportunity to develop not only domestic destinations, but also to attract foreign visitors to the tourist destination.

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